

THE ROLE OF THE SEMANTIC FIELD “SOCIAL NETWORK” IN THE SYSTEM OF LINGUISTIC UNITS OF MASS MEDIA

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Abstract. *This article explains what mass media is, the law on it, and the importance of mass media today. In addition, there is a description of media types. The article provides information about the language of mass media. A brief introduction to the term “medialinguistics”, which has recently entered linguistics, has been given, and through this term, the media language has been touched upon. The means of “social network” which is part of the mass media and considered one of its elements has been discussed. Information has been given on the features of social network platforms that distinguish them from other types of mass media. The most used language units in some of the social network platforms, including Telegram, Facebook, and Instagram platforms, have been discussed. The article has also briefly mentioned the semantic field.*

Keywords: *mass media, social network, semantic field, Telegram, Facebook, Instagram, medialinguistics, visual, auditory, audiovisual.*

INTRODUCTION

Today, one of the new topics in modern linguistics is medialinguistics, that is, the language of the mass media which is one of the areas being studied. The article has provided information about the language characteristics of the mass media and its types. Media types are divided into printed media and electronic media. Newspapers, magazines, and newsletters are included in written mass media, and electronic mass media include television, radio, video programs, and websites of telecommunication networks. Nowadays, electronic means are widely used compared to printed mass media. This is due to the convenience, ease and affordability of websites. Currently, any kind of news and information in the world can be easily found out through social networks such as Telegram, Facebook or Instagram. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “About Mass Media” of 2007 also provides the following: “Periodic distribution of public information with a permanent name and in printed form (newspapers, magazines, newsletters, bulletins, etc.) and (or) in electronic form (television, radio, video, newsreel programs, websites on public telecommunication networks) published or broadcast at least once every six months (here in after referred to as broadcast) and other forms of periodic distribution of public information is a mass media”. [5]

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

A number of scientific studies have been conducted on mass media, and it is still considered one of the areas that need to be studied. The reason is that this field is one of the fields that develops gradually with the development of technology. In the article, a model has been taken from the scientific works and articles of several researchers, and explained through examples. Sh.Normurodova touched upon the types of mass media in her article named “Lexical features of mass media in English and Uzbek”. D.Isakova’s knowledge of media language was used in the article “Medialinguistics”. The term “social network” was used in A.Bayrambayeva’s article “Use

of social networks in the educational process” about the advent of the Internet. In addition, the article provides information about the types of mass media, and M.Toshkanboyeva’s article “The role and importance of mass media in the life of today’s society” has been used as a source.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The mission of the mass media is to share information to the public. Therefore, the main goal and mission of mass media is to distribute information to the population at least once every six months. From this we can understand that mass media differ in the distribution of information or news according to their types (TV, radio, newspaper, social network). If information is rarely broadcasted or published on TV or radio and in newspapers and magazines, news can be given daily on social networking sites. Therefore, the role of mass media in human life is incomparable. So, we include social media sites from newspapers, magazines, television, radio to Facebook, Instagram, Twitter. These social networking platforms are the latest modern means of information dissemination. Recently, Facebook or Instagram is more widely used than newspapers, magazines or radios because it is convenient and easy to get news or information. In the article, social media tools are singled out and emphasized. Social networks are one of the elements of mass media.

Mass media are all types of media technologies that convey information to general public. It has several types:

1. Visual (press and internet)
2. Auditory (radio and television)
3. Audiovisual (television)[4]

Media language is, firstly, the whole set of texts produced and distributed by mass media; secondly, a stable interval system characterized by a certain set of linguo-stylistic features and signs; and finally, special mixed signal systems with a certain ratio of verbal and audiovisual components specific to each mass media - print, radio, television, The Internet.[3]

Today, mass media are used by people many times a day. For this reason, the term media language appears today in linguistics and is called “medialinguistics”. It follows from its name that “media” is information (mass media), “linguistics” is the subject of linguistics. So, medialinguistics is a field that comprehensively studies the language of mass media.

One of the most important conditions for the emergence of medialinguistics are:

- in particular, the rapid growth of information and communication technologies (ICT), manifested in the creation of a global media network;
- formation and development of a single information space as a new virtual environment of text communication;
- formation and scientific understanding of the concept of “media language”, determining its functional and stylistic features and internal structure;
- to realize the need for a comprehensive approach to the study of speech in mass media based on the joint efforts of representatives of various humanities;
- consideration of media language learning within media studies;
- a new independent science, the topic of which is a comprehensive analysis of the historical development, current state and characteristics of the entire mass communication complex.[3]

One of the reasons for the rapid development of social media platforms, which are part of mass media, is that it is easier and more convenient for people to get information or news than television, radio or newspaper. Social networks have become a means of connecting people from different parts of the world, besides, they have become the fastest means of spreading

communication between countries. At first, we understood only magazines and newspapers by mass media. As a result of the development of technologies, radios and televisions were created and served as another means of information delivery for people, more convenient than the previous ones. In addition, today's social network platforms, which are part of the mass media, serve as tools that deliver information in the most convenient and easy way.

The term "social network" was coined by Manneder School sociologist James Barnes in 1954 with the advent of the Internet, and indeed modern Internet networks.[1] Social networks, which are part of mass media, are of great importance. This is because, like other mass media, they share information and spread news. Therefore, social network platforms are one of the elements of the mass media system.

It has 5 main types according to the typology of mass media, as noted in modern theoretical sources. These are: the press (newspapers, magazines, newsletters, etc.), radio, television, news agencies, as well as Internet sites. Internet websites, which today attract the attention of many people, or rather, appear as a special means of mass information, are distinguished by their speed and breadth of possibilities compared to other types.[6]

The emergence of social networks is of great importance in the lives of modern people. They play a very important role in our life for communication and information exchange. Examples of widely used social networks in Uzbekistan for people of all ages are Facebook, Instagram, and Telegram. Social network platforms have become a part of people's lives. They serve to exchange communication between people, peoples and nationalities of the whole world. Social networks allow people to share ideas and interests, and make new friends. In general, we can call the social network a new era of communication.

The social network, which is considered an element of the mass media, has several differences from the rest of the mass media:

- **Convenience**: it is a convenient way to find videos, pictures, news or information about a person (life of celebrities) through social networking platforms. People can communicate with each other by text or voice;
- **Convenience**: You can find news or get information about interesting facts anytime, anywhere through Telegram, Facebook, Instagram or Twitter.
- **It is possible to find information or exchange information**: in this case, a person can find an answer to a question related to a topic of interest. In this case, for example, one can become a member of a group or channel through Telegram or Instagram platforms and get an opinion from an expert or find answers to his questions. For example, in case of problems related to work or study, legal services one can get advice by joining existing groups and channels.

In the dissertation "Functional-semantic study of the semantic field of religious and divine concepts", Z.H.Haydarov puts forward the following ideas about the semantic field: there is a commonality between them, if there is no similarity or commonality between them, then they are not words belonging to the same semantic field".[2]

Telegram is an instant messaging tool. In addition to text messaging, ordinary users can send each other images, videos, audio and various files up to 2GB in size, make voice and video calls, participate in voice and video chats in channels and groups.[7]

Facebook is a type of social network, where everyone has their own personal account, where they can upload photos, videos, and post. Through this platform, you can make friends,

communicate, comment on certain posts. There are also dedicated channels that you can subscribe to and follow. It is currently the most popular social networking tool.

Instagram is a social network tool where you can have your own personal account or channel, communicate, and keep up with news, just like Facebook.

CONCLUSION

Our research shows that mass media play a very important role in human life. People use mass media many times a day. The reasons for using mass media are varied, including keeping up with news, communicating, sharing information, etc. In modern linguistics, media language is referred to as “medialinguistics” and is a comprehensive study of media language. There are types of mass media, divided into print and electronic types. Mass media includes newspapers, radios, social networking sites and tools.

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